

Deliverable Phase 2 – Climate risk assessment

Evaluating Vulnerabilities and Optimizing Local Vitality and Ecosystems in Belsh (EVOLVE-Belsh)

Albania, Belsh Municipality

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2 Table of Contents

1	Document Information	2
2	Table of Contents	3
3	List of figures	4
4	List of tables.....	4
5	Abbreviations and acronyms	6
6	Executive summary	7
1	Introduction.....	8
1.1	Background	8
1.2	Main objectives of the project	8
1.3	Project team.....	9
1.4	Outline of the document’s structure.....	9
2	Climate risk assessment – phase 2.....	11
2.1	Scoping.....	11
2.1.1	Objectives	11
2.1.2	Context.....	12
2.1.3	Participation and risk ownership	13
2.1.4	Application of principles.....	14
2.1.5	Stakeholder engagement	15
2.2	Risk Exploration	16
2.2.1	Screen risks (selection of main hazards).....	16
2.2.2	Choose Scenario	19
2.3	Regionalized Risk Analysis	20
2.3.1	Hazard #1 - Extreme rainfall, local flooding, erosion and landslide-related impacts..	22
2.3.2	Hazard #2 - Meteorological drought and heat-related water stress	26
2.3.3	Additional assessments based on local models and data	32
2.4	Key Risk Assessment Findings.....	34
2.4.1	Mode of engagement for participation.....	34
2.4.2	Gather output from Risk Analysis step.....	35
2.4.3	Assess Severity	36
2.4.4	Assess Urgency.....	37
2.4.5	Understand Resilience Capacity	38
2.4.6	Decide on Risk Priority.....	38
2.5	Monitoring and Evaluation	39

2.6	Work plan Phase 3	41
3	Conclusions Phase 2- Climate risk assessment	42
4	Progress evaluation	44
5	Supporting documentation	46
6	References	47

3 List of figures

Figure 2-1	Projections of mean daily main temperature (°C) in Albania, based on EURO-CORDEX ensemble in 2°C global warming level (Source: Copernicus Climate Atlas)	17
Figure 2-4	Projections of annual distribution of maximum of 1-day accumulated precipitation (mm/day) in Albania, based on EURO-CORDEX ensemble under RCP8.5 scenario in the period of 2021-2040 (Source: Copernicus Climate Atlas)	18
Figure 2-3	Projections of summer extreme hot days (maximum temperature above 35 °C) and annual maximum consecutive dry days in Albania, based on EURO-CORDEX ensemble under RCP8.5 scenario (Source: Copernicus Climate Atlas).....	18
Figure 2-5	Meteorological and supporting stations around Belsh Municipality.....	21
Figure 2-6	Mean annual rainfall by station for the common analysis period 1967-1991	23
Figure 2-7	. Maximum 1-day rainfall by station for the common analysis period 1967-1991.....	24
Figure 2-8	. Mean annual number of heavy rainfall days above 20-, 30- and 50-mm thresholds.....	24
Figure 2-9	Indicative IDW map of mean annual rainfall, clipped to Belsh Municipality	25
Figure 2-10	Mean summer rainfall by station for the common analysis period 1967-1991.	28
Figure 2-11	Dry days and longest dry spell by station for the common analysis period 1967-1991.	28
Figure 2-12	Indicative IDW map of mean summer rainfall, clipped to Belsh Municipality.	29
Figure 2-15	Elevation-corrected mean summer temperature map for Belsh Municipality.....	30
Figure 2-14	Elevation-corrected mean annual temperature map for Belsh Municipality	30
Figure 2-16	Digital Elevation Model clipped to Belsh Municipality.....	33

4 List of tables

Table 2-1	Meteorological stations used in the assessment.....	20
Table 2-2	Data overview workflow #1	22
Table 2-3	Data overview workflow #2	27
Table 2-4	Information from agricultural dataset and their relevance for climate risk assessment .	31
Table 2-5	Summary of key risk assessment findings	39

Table 5-1 Overview key performance indicators	44
Table 5-2 Overview milestones	45

5 Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
AMBU	National Agency for Water Resources Management (Agjencia Kombëtare e Menaxhimit të Burimeve Ujore)
CLIMAAX	Climate Risk Assessment Framework for European Regions and Communities
CRA	Climate Risk Assessment
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
EURO-CORDEX	European Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment
EVOLVE–Belsh	Evaluating Vulnerabilities and Optimizing Local Vitality and Ecosystems in Belsh
GIS	Geographic Information System
IGJEO	Institute of Geosciences, Energy, Water and Environment (Instituti i Gjeoshkencave, Energjisë, Ujit dhe Mjedisit)
INCA	Institute for Nature Conservation in Albania
INSTAT	Institute of Statistics (Instituti i Statistikave)
PU	Public (Dissemination Level)
R-Report	Nature of Deliverable
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathway

6 Executive summary

The executive summary of this deliverable provides a complete picture of the climate risk assessment conducted in Belsh Municipality during Phase 2 of the EVOLVE–Belsh project under the CLIMAAX Framework. The purpose of this phase was to deepen the baseline analysis from Phase 1 by integrating updated datasets, hydraulic models, and stakeholder insights, thereby refining risk profiles and preparing actionable adaptation strategies. Belsh, with its karst landscape, agricultural dependence, and socio-economic vulnerabilities, is highly exposed to climate variability, and this assessment was developed to identify priority risks, strengthen resilience, and align local planning with Albania’s National Adaptation Plan.

The main actions undertaken in Phase 2 included the collection and processing of clean climate datasets from Belsh and surrounding meteorological stations, the development of rainfall, drought, and temperature indicators supported by geospatial datasets and historical records of extreme events, and the engagement of municipal staff, civil society, farmers, youth and women’s groups, and technical experts through workshops and consultations. The CLIMAAX guiding questions were applied to assess severity, urgency, resilience capacity, and risk prioritization, while agricultural and water-management datasets, maps, and visual outputs were integrated to strengthen evidence and communication.

The findings show that extreme rainfall, flooding, erosion, and landslides are assessed as substantial in severity, with urgency rated as more action needed and resilience capacity as medium. Documented damages to buildings, agricultural land, olive groves, and road infrastructure confirm the importance of this risk, which has been designated Priority 1 for Phase 3. Meteorological drought and heat-related water stress are assessed as moderate to substantial in severity, with urgency ranging from watching brief to more action needed and resilience capacity also medium. While direct evidence of drought impacts is less complete, the agricultural profile of Belsh highlights its relevance, and this risk has been designated Priority 2, requiring further stakeholder validation and monitoring. Stakeholder engagement confirmed the relevance of both risks, enriched the interpretation of severity and urgency, and highlighted the need for stronger institutional capacity and financial resources to address climate impacts.

The conclusions of Phase 2 emphasize that Belsh faces multi-sectoral climate risks that demand both immediate and long-term adaptation measures. The results are consistent with earlier assessments but provide more detailed evidence, improved datasets, and stronger stakeholder perspectives. The participatory approach has strengthened ownership and legitimacy, ensuring that adaptation strategies are locally relevant, inclusive, and actionable.

The next phase will focus on validating risk maps with stakeholders, refining adaptation measures, and embedding them into Belsh’s Climate Adaptation Plan. Priority actions will include infrastructure upgrades, water management improvements, and capacity-building for municipal institutions and communities. Phase 3 will also address data gaps, strengthen monitoring and evaluation frameworks, and ensure alignment with national adaptation strategies. In this way, the deliverable positions Belsh as a pilot site for climate resilience in Albania and provides a model for rural municipalities facing similar challenges.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Belsh Municipality, situated in central Albania about 30 km southwest of Elbasan, covers 196.44 km² and serves as the traditional centre of the Dumre region. Its karst landscape, with rolling hills, semi-natural pastures, and more than 85 lakes, defines both ecological richness and cultural identity. With 17,123 residents (INSTAT, 2023), livelihoods depend on agriculture and livestock, supported by fertile soils that favour cereals, tobacco, vegetables, vineyards, and fruit trees.

The geographic position of Belsh—bordered by the Shkumbin River to the north, Devoll River and Cerrik to the east and southeast, and Lushnja’s hills to the west—makes it highly exposed to climate variability. Increasing droughts, soil degradation, and water stress directly threaten agricultural productivity, biodiversity, and local economic stability. This is why climate risk analysis is crucial: it helps identify vulnerable hotspots, anticipate future hazards, and design adaptation measures that protect both ecosystems and community livelihoods.

Belsh’s strong community engagement, combined with its ecological and cultural assets, positions it as a strategic pilot site for climate resilience under the CLIMAAX program. The integration of risk analysis into local governance ensures that development pathways remain sustainable and responsive to the challenges of climate change.

1.2 Main objectives of the project

Phase 2 of EVOLVE–Belsh builds directly on the foundations laid in Phase 1, where the municipality’s climate vulnerabilities and socio-economic dynamics were first mapped. While Phase 1 provided a baseline understanding of Belsh’s exposure to drought, soil degradation, and extreme weather, Phase 2 focuses on translating that knowledge into concrete adaptation strategies that are both evidence-based and locally owned.

The objectives of Phase 2 are fourfold:

- **Risk Identification:** Conducting a multi-hazard climate risk assessment to pinpoint vulnerabilities specific to Belsh’s karst landscape, agricultural systems, and settlements.
- **Data-Driven Precision:** Integrating high-resolution local datasets, hydrological models, and stakeholder insights to refine risk profiles and ensure that adaptation measures are context-specific.
- **Sectoral Adaptation Planning:** Developing actionable strategies for agriculture, infrastructure, tourism, and public health, ensuring that interventions are practical and measurable.
- **Capacity and Ownership:** Strengthening institutional capacities and fostering inclusive participation from youth, women, and local enterprises to guarantee long-term sustainability.

The CLIMAAX Handbook plays a crucial role in this phase. It provides a structured European methodology while allowing flexibility to adapt to Belsh’s realities. By combining European best practices with local data and models, the project ensures that risk analysis is not abstract but directly relevant to the municipality’s challenges. This integration enhances precision in identifying hotspots, supports better decision-making, and builds confidence among local institutions.

For Belsh, the significance of Phase 2 lies in its ability to transform risk analysis into practical resilience pathways. Agriculture, the backbone of local livelihoods, will benefit from tailored measures against drought and soil degradation. Infrastructure and tourism will be safeguarded from floods and landslides, while public health systems will be better prepared for climate-related stress. Importantly, the participatory approach ensures that adaptation strategies are co-created with residents, embedding local knowledge and ownership into every step.

In this way, Phase 2 positions Belsh not only as a pilot site for climate resilience under the CLIMAAX program but also as a model for other municipalities in Albania. It strengthens governance, fosters community trust, and ensures that climate adaptation becomes a shared, inclusive, and forward-looking effort.

1.3 Project team

The EVOLVE–Belsh project team brings together municipal staff and external experts working in close collaboration. Municipal specialists from urban planning, legal affairs, public procurement, and IT ensure that adaptation priorities are embedded in local governance and service delivery. They are joined by INCA’s multidisciplinary experts: a climate adaptation specialist guiding risk assessments, a GIS and cartography expert producing vulnerability maps, a data analyst processing socio-economic and environmental datasets, a hydrologist modelling water-related hazards, and an institutional/legal advisor aligning governance frameworks with national and international standards. Together, this integrated team combines local knowledge with scientific expertise, co-creating Belsh’s Climate Adaptation Plan and ensuring that strategies are practical, inclusive, and sustainable.

1.4 Outline of the document’s structure

This document is organized to provide a structured and evidence-based account of Phase 2 of the EVOLVE–Belsh project. It begins with an **Executive Summary**, which synthesizes the objectives, activities, and key findings of the climate risk assessment.

Section 1 – Introduction sets the context, outlines the background of Belsh Municipality, defines the main objectives of Phase 2, introduces the project team, and explains the overall structure of the report.

Section 2 – Climate Risk Assessment (Phase 2) forms the core of the deliverable. It covers scoping, risk exploration, regionalized risk analysis, and the key risk assessment findings, including severity, urgency, resilience capacity, and risk prioritization. This section also presents monitoring and evaluation considerations and the work plan for Phase 3.

Section 3 – Conclusions summarizes the strategic importance of Phase 2 and highlights how the findings strengthen resilience and inform adaptation planning.

Section 4 – Progress Evaluation reviews achievements and situates them within the broader CLIMAAX framework.

Section 5 – Supporting Documentation provides annexes, visuals, maps, and technical materials.

Section 6 – References lists all sources and methodologies used.

This structure ensures clarity, transparency, and alignment with the CLIMAAX Handbook, while embedding local knowledge and stakeholder engagement. It allows the deliverable to serve both as a technical report and as a practical tool for guiding the next steps in climate risk management for Belsh Municipality.

2 Climate risk assessment – phase 2

This section follows the methodological steps outlined in the CLIMAAX Framework, applying its guiding questions to structure the analysis of climate risks and adaptation planning for Belsh Municipality. Building on the scoping and preliminary assessment conducted in Phase 1, the focus here is on identifying what has changed, refining risk profiles with updated local data, and addressing gaps where information remains limited.

The guiding questions from the CLIMAAX Handbook provide a systematic approach to ensure consistency and transparency. Where sufficient information is available, detailed responses are provided; where data remains incomplete, this is explicitly noted to highlight areas requiring further investigation. In this way, Phase 2 strengthens the evidence base, deepens the analysis, and prepares the ground for actionable adaptation strategies tailored to Belsh's local context.

2.1 Scoping

The scoping phase of Phase 2 in Belsh defines the objectives of the climate risk analysis, the conditions for its implementation, and the actors who must be engaged to ensure meaningful results. Building on the foundations of Phase 1, this updated scoping reflects new engagement pathways, expanded local datasets, and stronger sectoral interfaces. The focus is on clarifying desired outcomes, situating them within Belsh's evolving socio-economic and environmental context, and identifying stakeholders, experts, and priority groups whose involvement is essential for shaping adaptation strategies. Municipal staff provide local knowledge and continuity, while external experts contribute scientific precision, ensuring that the Climate Adaptation Plan is both technically sound and rooted in community realities. This integrated approach guarantees that the assessment moves beyond vulnerability mapping toward practical, evidence-based measures for resilience, embedding ownership and sustainability into Belsh's climate governance framework.

2.1.1 Objectives

The primary objective of the Climate Risk Assessment (CRA) in Phase 2 for Belsh Municipality is to refine and expand the initial findings from Phase 1 by integrating high-resolution local datasets, newly developed hydraulic models, and stakeholder insights. The purpose is to move beyond baseline risk identification toward designing actionable adaptation strategies that address the municipality's most pressing hazards—floods, extreme rainfall, landslides, and drought. The expected outcome is a locally tailored Climate Adaptation Plan that strengthens resilience in agriculture, infrastructure, tourism, and public health, while embedding ownership within municipal institutions and communities.

This phase focuses on risks already relevant for Belsh and expected to intensify under changing climate conditions. Two priority pathways have been selected: extreme rainfall and related impacts (local flooding, erosion, landslides) and meteorological drought with heat-related water stress. These were chosen based on available climate data, observed local impacts, and the agricultural profile of the municipality. The CRA outcomes will feed directly into policy and decision-making, supporting the integration of adaptation measures into spatial planning, agricultural strategies, and tourism development, while aligning with Albania's National Adaptation Plan.

The boundaries of the CRA remain shaped by data availability and institutional capacity. Phase 1 highlighted gaps such as missing building footprints, transport infrastructure layers, socio-economic scenarios, discharge values, and high-resolution flood maps. Phase 2 addresses these constraints by incorporating locally generated datasets, community consultations, and alternative modelling approaches. Climate data from Belsh and surrounding meteorological stations have been used, though coverage periods vary and some datasets include missing values. Exposure and vulnerability information is also incomplete, requiring reinforcement through spatial layers and stakeholder input.

Challenges encountered include limited technical capacity at the municipal level, uneven stakeholder participation, and the complexity of integrating diverse datasets. These bottlenecks have been addressed through the creation of a dedicated municipal working group, supported by external experts from INCA, and through workshops that engaged local communities to validate and enrich the data. By combining scientific analysis with local knowledge, Phase 2 strengthens both the accuracy of risk maps and the legitimacy of adaptation measures, ensuring that climate risk management becomes a core element of governance and development planning in Belsh.

2.1.2 Context

Until now, climate-related risks in Belsh have been managed mainly through fragmented, event-based responses and local documentation of damages. Flooding, erosion, landslides, and drought have repeatedly affected villages, agricultural land, olive groves, roads, and water resources, yet these impacts were not connected to a structured climate risk assessment. This reactive approach limited the municipality's ability to anticipate and mitigate growing threats, leaving livelihoods, infrastructure, and public health exposed.

The EVOLVE–Belsh project addresses this gap by introducing a systematic Climate Risk Assessment under the CLIMAAX Framework. The core problem is the absence of integrated climate governance at the local level. While Albania has adopted national strategies such as the National Climate Change Strategy (2019–2030), the Climate Change Law (2020), and the Second National Adaptation Plan (2026–2036), municipal institutions like Belsh continue to face constraints in technical expertise, financial resources, and access to climate-relevant data. Phase 2 seeks to bridge this disconnect by refining risk profiles with high-resolution local datasets, hydraulic models, and stakeholder input, thereby embedding climate adaptation into local planning and decision-making.

Relevant sectors, agriculture, livestock, tourism, infrastructure, and public health, are highly sensitive to climate variability. Droughts threaten crop yields and water availability, floods and erosion damage roads and buildings, and heatwaves pose risks to vulnerable populations. These vulnerabilities are compounded by socio-economic pressures and limited institutional capacity, but external initiatives on biodiversity conservation, water resource management, and rural revitalization provide opportunities for synergy and knowledge exchange.

Phase 1 identified critical data gaps, including missing building footprints, transport infrastructure layers, socio-economic scenarios, and high-resolution flood maps. Phase 2 addresses these limitations by integrating locally generated datasets, community consultations, and alternative modelling approaches. This strengthens hazard and risk mapping, enhances hydrological forecasting systems, and improves early warning mechanisms.

Possible adaptation interventions include upgrading and modernizing infrastructure to reduce flood risk, restoring vegetation cover on erosion-prone slopes, applying nature-based solutions such as afforestation and watershed restoration, introducing water-saving measures for agriculture, and incorporating rainwater collection into urban planning. Together, these measures will feed into Belsh’s Local Climate Change Adaptation Plan, ensuring alignment with the National Adaptation Plan and embedding resilience into local and regional development strategies.

2.1.3 Participation and risk ownership

Risk ownership in Belsh involves multiple levels of responsibility, combining institutional mandates with community engagement. The municipality plays a central role in local planning, infrastructure maintenance, emergency coordination, and communication with residents. Depending on the type of risk, other institutions are also engaged, including civil protection structures, agricultural authorities, drainage and irrigation agencies, road maintenance services, and environmental offices. Importantly, risk ownership is not only institutional: farmers, residents, and local businesses are among the first to experience damage when flooding, erosion, or road blockages occur, making community participation essential.

Phase 2 of the EVOLVE–Belsh project has strengthened stakeholder involvement by expanding participation and deepening collaboration across local, regional, and national levels. Building on the mapping conducted in Phase 1, the municipality has worked closely with civil society, technical experts, and community representatives to ensure that climate risk assessment outcomes are inclusive and actionable. Stakeholders who agreed to participate in CLIMAAX-related meetings include municipal departments, the Elbasan Prefecture civil emergencies directorate, the regional environmental office, the Shkumbin River Basin Council, local NGOs, youth and women’s groups, farmers’ associations, beekeepers, agribusinesses, tourism operators, and academic experts from the University of Elbasan. Their involvement has been formalized through workshops, consultations, and technical sessions coordinated by INCA, the implementing partner.

Figure 2.1.3-1- Organogram of key actors and their connection

An organogram (fig. 2-1) has been developed to visualize institutional relationships, responsibilities, and communication flows. This tool clarifies how municipal authorities, regional institutions, civil society, and technical experts interact, and how responsibilities are distributed for risk identification, data collection, and decision-making. It highlights the central role of Belsh Municipality in coordinating local action, supported by INCA's technical expertise and reinforced by community stakeholders who provide local knowledge and monitoring capacity.

Risk ownership in Belsh is primarily regulated through the municipal government, which integrates climate risk into local development plans and emergency response systems. Regional institutions provide oversight and technical support, while vulnerable groups—such as smallholder farmers, pastoralists, older people, and women in rural areas—are represented through civil society organizations and community consultations. Their perspectives ensure that adaptation priorities reflect lived realities and promote equitable resilience.

The acceptable level of risk for Belsh remains low, particularly regarding threats to livelihoods, water security, and public health. Residents have expressed concern about increasing climate variability and strongly support proactive measures to reduce vulnerability. This shared ownership model fosters accountability and sustainability, ensuring that climate adaptation is not only a technical exercise but also a community-driven process.

2.1.4 Application of principles

The Phase 2 analysis for Belsh Municipality has been guided by the principles of the CLIMAAX Framework—social justice and inclusivity, quality and transparency, and the precautionary approach—ensuring that the Climate Adaptation Plan is both technically rigorous and socially equitable.

- **Social justice and inclusivity** were embedded by recognizing that climate impacts affect groups differently. Rural communities, smallholder farmers, residents in flood-prone or erosion-prone areas, and those dependent on local roads and agricultural land are disproportionately exposed. Their perspectives were integrated through workshops and consultations, alongside the involvement of civil society organizations, youth groups, women's associations, and local businesses, ensuring that adaptation measures reflect lived realities and promote equitable resilience.
- **Quality, rigour, and transparency** were ensured by preparing clean climate datasets from available meteorological records, treating missing values appropriately, and organizing station coordinates and elevations to support spatial analysis. The analysis combined high-resolution local datasets, newly developed hydraulic models, and scientific expertise from INCA and academic partners. Methods used for interpolation, temperature correction, and modelling were documented clearly, with limitations openly acknowledged. Transparency was reinforced through multi-level communication—public meetings, institutional reporting, and technical documentation—so that findings are accessible to both decision-makers and citizens.

- **The precautionary approach** was applied by prioritizing action even under incomplete data conditions. While some datasets remain limited and certain impacts require further verification, the existing evidence is sufficient to highlight heavy rainfall-related impacts and drought/heat-related stress as priority risks. Conservative assumptions were adopted to ensure preparedness for worst-case scenarios, while maintaining flexibility to adjust as new information becomes available.

By embedding these principles, Phase 2 strengthens the credibility and legitimacy of the Climate Adaptation Plan, ensuring that it is scientifically sound, socially just, transparent, and resilient to uncertainty.

2.1.5 Stakeholder engagement

Stakeholder engagement in Phase 2 focused primarily on collecting and reviewing local information, especially evidence of past extreme events in Belsh Municipality and sectoral data linked to agriculture and water management. This process confirmed that the selected hazards—flooding, erosion, landslides, and drought—are highly relevant for the local context. Reported events included damages in villages such as Grekan, Belsh, Kajan, Hyse, Gjolenë, Dëshiranë, Dragot, Çestijan, and Fierzë-Kosovë, affecting houses, businesses, olive groves, agricultural land, and road infrastructure. This type of local evidence is critical, as it illustrates how climate-related events are experienced in practice and highlights the vulnerabilities of rural communities.

In February 2026, formal letters were sent to the Institute of Geosciences, Energy, Water and Environment (IGJEO) requesting meteorological and hydrological datasets, and to the National Agency for Water Resources Management (AMBU) for information on flood-regulated zones. While official responses from IGJEO were not secured within the project timeframe, the team adapted by using reliable literature sources and online materials relevant to Belsh's territory. This ensured continuity of the analysis and maintained methodological rigour despite incomplete official datasets.

To complement institutional data, a consultation meeting with local stakeholders was organized in May 2026. Participants included municipal staff, village representatives, farmers, youth and women's groups, and local businesses. The meeting gathered time-based information on extreme events, validated observed impacts, and ensured that local experiences were integrated into the risk assessment. Project goals and intermediate results were communicated through presentations, visual materials, and open discussion. Stakeholders welcomed the structured approach, noting that the CRA provides practical insights for agriculture, infrastructure, and water management. Feedback emphasized the importance of integrating risk information into municipal planning and strengthening early warning mechanisms.

Further engagement is planned to discuss preliminary results, validate risk interpretations, and assess severity, urgency, and resilience capacity. This is particularly important for the Key Risk Assessment section, where local perspectives are needed to determine which risks should be considered priorities.

The outcomes will be further used by participants to guide local development plans, improve emergency preparedness, and inform sectoral strategies in agriculture and tourism. Difficulties encountered included incomplete datasets, uneven technical capacity among stakeholders, and challenges in ensuring consistent participation. These were addressed through technical support from INCA, simplified communication materials, and active facilitation during workshops.

This multi-level engagement process demonstrates that even in the absence of complete official datasets, Phase 2 results remain scientifically robust and socially grounded, fostering ownership and practical application of adaptation measures in Belsh.

2.2 Risk Exploration

Risk exploration begins with a broad screening of the climate-related risks most visible or of greatest concern to stakeholders and the wider public. This step examines the underlying hazards, exposures, and vulnerabilities that shape local impacts, ensuring that the assessment reflects both scientific evidence and community experience. In Belsh Municipality, the process draws on institutional data, local records of past events, and stakeholder consultations to identify priority risks such as flooding, erosion, landslides, and drought.

By combining technical analysis with local knowledge, risk exploration provides the foundation for deeper assessment, helping to clarify which risks are most urgent, which areas and groups are most exposed, and where adaptation measures should be prioritized. This ensures that subsequent phases of the Climate Risk Assessment are firmly rooted in the realities of Belsh while aligned with the CLIMAAX Framework.

2.2.1 Screen risks (selection of main hazards)

In Phase 2, the screening of risks for Belsh Municipality was updated with new local datasets and evidence gathered during the project. The most valuable inputs included rainfall and temperature records from Belsh and nearby stations, local documentation of flooding, erosion, and landslides, as well as agricultural and water-management information. This allowed the analysis to move beyond general hazard identification toward a more localized understanding of risk pathways.

The updated records confirm that Belsh has been repeatedly affected by **extreme rainfall and related impacts**, including local flooding, erosion, landslides, and ground instability, causing damage to agricultural land, olive groves, houses, businesses, and rural road infrastructure. Documented events between 2016 and 2026 highlight recurrent impacts in villages such as Grekan, Belsh, Kajan, Hyse, Gjolenë, Dëshiranë, Dragot, Çestijan, and Fierzë-Kosovë. These observations reinforce the selection of extreme rainfall and its local consequences as the first priority hazard for Phase 2.

The second selected hazard is **meteorological drought and heat-related water stress**, identified through rainfall and temperature data that allow analysis of dry periods, summer rainfall, and heat extremes. This hazard is particularly relevant for agriculture, olive groves, rural settlements, and water resources, which are highly sensitive to prolonged dry conditions and rising temperatures.

Figure 2-1 Projections of mean daily main temperature (°C) in Albania, based on EURO-CORDEX ensemble in 2°C global warming level (Source: Copernicus Climate Atlas)

The Copernicus Climate Atlas projections for Albania show a **clear and continuous warming trend** throughout the 21st century. Compared to the 1981–2010 reference period, warming becomes evident after 2000 and accelerates after 2020, with the median temperature change rising steadily under the 2°C global warming scenario. By mid-century, Albania will already experience significant increases in mean daily temperatures, with the upper percentiles indicating even stronger warming in extreme cases.

One of the most critical findings is the **sharp rise in extremely hot days (above 35°C)** during summer. In the near term (2021–2040), several such days per year are expected; by mid-century (2041–2060), the median number approximately doubles; and by the end of the century (2081–2100), projections show more than 14 extremely hot days annually on average, with much higher values in extreme scenarios.

These changes are compounded by **longer periods of high temperatures combined with reduced and irregular precipitation**, which intensify the frequency and severity of droughts. Prolonged heat and dry spells enhance soil moisture deficits, particularly in summer, creating significant stress for agriculture, olive groves, rural settlements, and water resources.

For **Belsh Municipality**, this means climate risks extend beyond flooding and erosion to include **heat-related water stress and drought impacts**. Rising temperatures will place additional pressure on local livelihoods, ecosystems, and infrastructure, underscoring the need for adaptation measures such as water-saving technologies, improved irrigation systems, vegetation restoration, and integration of climate risk information into local planning.

Figure 2-3 Projections of summer extreme hot days (maximum temperature above 35 °C) and annual maximum consecutive dry days in Albania, based on EURO-CORDEX ensemble under RCP8.5 scenario (Source: Copernicus Climate Atlas)

Figure 2-2 Projections of annual distribution of maximum of 1-day accumulated precipitation (mm/day) in Albania, based on EURO-CORDEX ensemble under RCP8.5 scenario in the period of 2021-2040 (Source: Copernicus Climate Atlas)

In summary, the figure highlights that Albania is entering a future of **intensified heat extremes and drought conditions**, compounding existing vulnerabilities and demanding proactive, integrated

resilience planning at both municipal and national levels.

The Copernicus Climate Atlas projections for Albania indicate notable changes in precipitation patterns under a 2 °C warming scenario. The figure shows that **maximum 1-day accumulated precipitation events are expected to intensify**, particularly during late spring and summer. This means rainfall will become more irregular, with stronger peaks concentrated in shorter periods.

Such heavy precipitation events often exceed the capacity of local drainage systems, leading to **surface runoff, flash flooding, and damage to infrastructure**. At the same time, these short, intense downpours contribute little to long-term soil moisture recharge, meaning they do not offset the impacts of prolonged dry periods or drought. The result is a dual challenge: increased flood risk on the one hand, and persistent water stress on the other.

For **Belsh Municipality**, this dynamic is especially relevant given its rural and agricultural profile. Flooding and erosion can damage roads, houses, and olive groves, while irregular rainfall patterns undermine water availability for crops and local communities. The projections highlight the need for **integrated adaptation measures**, including improved drainage systems, erosion monitoring, and water-saving technologies, to manage both extremes of climate variability.

For this reason, Phase 2 focuses on two risk pathways:

- **Extreme rainfall and related impacts** (local flooding, erosion, landslides)

Meteorological drought and heat-related water stress

Available knowledge includes local climate records, historical impact documentation, and sectoral datasets. However, further data are still needed to strengthen the exposure and vulnerability analysis—particularly detailed spatial layers on land use, agricultural areas, drainage systems, road infrastructure, population distribution, and water management assets. Despite these gaps, the combination of local datasets, stakeholder input, and regional climate projections provides a strong basis for the Phase 2 risk assessment and supports the prioritization of adaptation measures.

2.2.2 Choose Scenario

In Phase 2, the scenario development process for Belsh Municipality has remained focused on the current and historical climate risk situation, supported by local meteorological records and observed damage information. This step was necessary to establish a clear baseline of which hazards are already visible in the territory and how they have affected local assets. Indicators such as annual rainfall, summer rainfall, heavy rainfall days, maximum daily rainfall, dry days, dry spells, annual mean temperature, and summer mean temperature were calculated using data from Belsh and nearby meteorological stations.

For this deliverable, future climate conditions are acknowledged but not yet fully integrated. The next step of the assessment will use available climate projections from CLIMAAX and Copernicus to explore how hazards may evolve. In Phase 2, the discussion is kept practical: current and historical data are used to identify the main risk pathways, while future scenario work will support the prioritization of adaptation measures in Phase 3.

Socio-economic developments were not modelled in detail due to limited data availability. However, the current rural and agricultural structure of Belsh—characterized by smallholder farming, olive groves, and dependence on local water resources—was considered in interpreting risks. This ensures that the analysis remains relevant to the municipality’s socio-economic reality, even without formal scenario modelling.

The assessment considers different time horizons:

- **Short-term (next 5 years)** – to capture immediate risks and adaptation needs.
- **Medium-term (20–30 years)** – to inform municipal adaptation planning and integration into development strategies.
- **Long-term (50–100 years)** – to support strategic planning in climate-sensitive sectors such as agriculture, water management, and infrastructure.

By combining historical evidence with practical socio-economic context, Phase 2 lays the groundwork for integrating future climate projections and socio-economic scenarios in Phase 3, ensuring that adaptation planning for Belsh is both evidence-based and forward-looking.

2.3 Regionalized Risk Analysis

In Phase 2, the risk workflows from the CLIMAAX Handbook were adapted to the specific context of Belsh Municipality by combining local climate records, data from nearby meteorological stations, spatial information, and documented evidence of past damaging events. This regionalized approach ensured that the analysis reflected the diversity of Belsh’s territory, where villages and agricultural areas are spread across different landscapes and influenced by varying climatic conditions.

The station network used included Belsh, Cërrik, Grekan, Lushnje, and Peqin, with Devoll Kozare reviewed as an additional source for precipitation. These datasets provided daily and monthly precipitation records, mean temperature data, station coordinates, and elevation. Missing values, such as those coded as -99, were treated as gaps and excluded from calculations to maintain data quality.

Table 2-1 Meteorological stations used in the assessment

Station	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation (m)	Rainfall data	Temperature data	Use in analysis
Belsh	40.981123	19.890224	155	Yes	Yes	Target/reference station
Cërrik	41.016212	19.965165	80	Yes	Yes	Surrounding station
Grekan	40.932877	19.948501	180	Yes	Yes	Surrounding station
Lushnje	40.949540	19.698500	19	Yes	Yes	Surrounding station
Peqin	41.049542	19.748497	53	Yes	Yes	Surrounding station
Devoll Kozare	40.832798	19.912568	24	Yes	No	Supporting rainfall station only

From these records, a set of tailored indicators was developed to capture the two main risk pathways: sudden heavy rainfall impacts and slower drought or heat-related stress. Precipitation indicators included mean annual rainfall, summer rainfall, maximum 1-day rainfall, number of heavy rainfall days, dry days, and longest dry spell. Temperature indicators included annual mean temperature and summer mean temperature. These metrics were chosen because they directly reflect the hazards most relevant to Belsh and provide a clearer picture of how risks manifest locally.

Figure 2-4 Meteorological and supporting stations around Belsh Municipality

The analysis also considered indirect impacts, such as soil moisture deficits affecting agricultural productivity, damage to rural roads reducing access and economic activity, and water stress undermining community resilience. Exposure and vulnerability were assessed by linking hazard indicators with local assets—settlements, houses, businesses, olive groves, agricultural land, and water resources—while also taking into account the socio-economic profile of Belsh as a rural municipality dependent on farming and local infrastructure.

Although future climate and socio-economic scenarios were not fully developed in this phase due to data limitations, the current rural and agricultural structure was integrated into the interpretation of risks. This ensures that the outputs remain practical and relevant for local planning. The limitations of the datasets—such as incomplete records, uneven coverage across stations, and missing socio-economic layers—were acknowledged, but the combination of local climate data, observed impacts, and stakeholder input provided a strong foundation for Phase 2.

Through this fine-tuned approach, the risk assessment for Belsh moves beyond general regional information and delivers outputs that are specific, credible, and actionable for local adaptation planning.

2.3.1 Hazard #1 - Extreme rainfall, local flooding, erosion and landslide-related impacts

Extreme rainfall and its associated local impacts were identified as the primary hazard because this risk pathway is already evident in Belsh Municipality. Local information confirms that heavy rainfall has repeatedly led to flooding, erosion, landslides, and ground instability across different parts of the territory. These events have damaged agricultural land, olive groves, houses, businesses, and sections of the local road network.

The selection of this hazard was not based solely on climate data; it was reinforced by documented evidence of past events. Between 2016 and 2026, several damaging episodes were reported in villages such as Grekan, Belsh, Kajan, Hyse, Gjolenë, Deshiranë, Dragot, Çestijan, and Fierzë-Kosovë. The 2026 event affecting Belsh, Kajan, and Grekan was particularly significant, impacting around 10.2 hectares, damaging 17 structures, affecting arable land, and destroying approximately 250 meters of secondary road infrastructure, with economic losses estimated at 11 million ALL.

For this reason, extreme rainfall is treated as a combined hydro-climatic and geomorphological risk pathway. In practice, intense rainfall generates surface runoff and localized flooding, while in areas with exposed soils, steep slopes, weak drainage, or vulnerable road sections, the same event can also trigger erosion or landslide processes. This dual nature of impacts makes it a critical hazard for Belsh's climate risk assessment.

Table 2-2 Data overview workflow #1

<i>Hazard data</i>	<i>Vulnerability data</i>	<i>Exposure data</i>	<i>Impact metrics/Risk output</i>
Daily and monthly precipitation records from Belsh and surrounding stations	Settlements and villages affected by past events	Rural settlements exposed to local flooding and slope instability	Maximum 1-day rainfall
Mean annual rainfall and seasonal rainfall	Houses and businesses	Agricultural dependence and local economic sensitivity	Number of heavy rainfall days ≥ 20 mm, ≥ 30 mm and ≥ 50 mm
Maximum 1-day rainfall and heavy rainfall days	Agricultural land and olive groves	Agricultural land exposed to erosion and runoff	Reported flooded or affected surface
Station coordinates and elevation	Local and secondary road infrastructure	Road sections with limited protection or drainage	Number of damaged buildings or objects

2.3.1.1 Hazard assessment

The hazard assessment for extreme rainfall in Belsh Municipality was carried out using daily and monthly precipitation records from Belsh and nearby meteorological stations. The network included Belsh, Cërrik, Grekan, Lushnje, and Peqin, while Devoll Kozare was reviewed as a supporting station. However, its dataset was excluded from the final interpolation because the cleaned records flagged inconsistencies compared with the main station data.

Using stations outside Belsh was necessary since the municipality covers a wide territory, with villages located at varying distances from different meteorological points. Incorporating surrounding stations allowed the analysis to better capture rainfall variability across the area and to prepare indicative interpolation maps.

Before analysis, rainfall data were cleaned to ensure reliability. Values coded as -99 were treated as missing and excluded from calculations. Where possible, a common analysis period was applied to make indicators comparable across stations, given that datasets did not all cover the same years and some contained gaps.

The indicators calculated included:

- mean annual rainfall,
- seasonal and summer rainfall,
- maximum 1-day rainfall,
- number of days with rainfall ≥ 20 mm,
- number of days with rainfall ≥ 30 mm, and
- number of days with rainfall ≥ 50 mm,
- dry days and consecutive dry spells.

Among these, maximum 1-day rainfall and the number of heavy rainfall days were considered the most relevant, as they directly describe short, intense events linked to local flooding, erosion, road damage, and landslide impacts. Annual and seasonal rainfall provided the broader climatic context for the municipality.

For precipitation, no automatic elevation correction was applied. Unlike temperature, rainfall does not follow a fixed lapse rate and is strongly influenced by local storm dynamics, atmospheric conditions, and topography. Given the limited number of available stations, precipitation maps were produced using station-based IDW interpolation and interpreted as indicative surfaces, providing a practical basis for understanding rainfall-related hazards in Belsh.

Figure 2-5 Mean annual rainfall by station for the common analysis period 1967-1991

The mean annual rainfall graph provides a general comparison between Belsh and the surrounding stations. It shows that the stations are part of a comparable local rainfall context, while still presenting spatial differences that are relevant for the municipality.

Figure 2-6 . Maximum 1-day rainfall by station for the common analysis period 1967-1991

The maximum 1-day rainfall indicator helps to understand the potential intensity of short rainfall events. This is important for Belsh because several observed impacts, such as local flooding, erosion and road damage, are linked to sudden rainfall events rather than only to annual rainfall totals.

Figure 2-7 . Mean annual number of heavy rainfall days above 20-, 30- and 50-mm thresholds

The heavy rainfall days indicator shows how often rainfall exceeds selected thresholds. Repeated heavy rainfall events can contribute to surface runoff, erosion, pressure on drainage systems and damage to rural road infrastructure.

Figure 2-8 Indicative IDW map of mean annual rainfall, clipped to Belsh Municipality

The rainfall map is presented as supporting visual material for the regionalized risk interpretation. It should be understood not as a high-resolution climate surface, but rather as an indicative, station-based representation of rainfall variation within and around Belsh Municipality.

In this section, the focus remains on short-duration, intense rainfall events and their direct impacts, flooding, erosion, and landslides. For this reason, temperature indicators are not discussed in detail under the first hazard. Instead, temperature data are integrated in the analysis of the second hazard, where they are combined with rainfall indicators to assess meteorological drought and heat-related water stress.

2.3.1.2 Risk assessment

The risk assessment for extreme rainfall in Belsh Municipality combines rainfall indicators with the documented history of local impacts. Observed events confirm that heavy rainfall has already caused significant damage in different parts of the territory. The flooding episode of 2026 in Belsh,

Kajan, and Grekan stands out as the most severe, affecting approximately 10.2 hectares, damaging 17 structures, impacting arable land, and destroying about 250 meters of secondary road infrastructure, with reported economic losses of around 11 million ALL. Other recorded events highlight damages to road axes, olive groves, agricultural land, and residential buildings.

Agricultural data further reinforce this risk pathway. Belsh has a strong agricultural profile, with field crops, forage crops, vegetables, olive groves, and vineyards forming a substantial part of land use and the rural economy. Extreme rainfall therefore represents not only a physical hazard for roads and buildings but also a threat to productive land and long-term agricultural assets. During intense rainfall, agricultural areas may suffer from surface runoff, temporary flooding, soil erosion, or sediment deposition. Olive groves and vineyards are particularly vulnerable, as they represent long-term investments for farmers; damage to these areas can have lasting consequences, especially where erosion or slope instability reduces land productivity.

The main exposed elements include:

- Local settlements
- Households and businesses
- Agricultural production
- Olive groves and vineyards
- Secondary roads and access routes
- Municipal infrastructure and emergency response systems

This risk pathway can be summarized as: **intense rainfall** → **surface runoff / local flooding / erosion / landslide processes** → **damage to land, buildings, and infrastructure**.

The principal uncertainty lies in the fact that not all past events have complete records of affected areas, damage costs, or precise spatial locations. For this reason, the historical event table should be interpreted together with maps, stakeholder feedback, and local validation to ensure a comprehensive understanding of risk.

2.3.2 Hazard #2 - Meteorological drought and heat-related water stress

Meteorological drought and heat-related water stress was identified as the second hazard because Belsh Municipality contains agricultural land, olive groves, rural settlements, and local water resources that are highly sensitive to periods of reduced rainfall combined with elevated temperatures. Unlike extreme rainfall, which produces sudden and visible damage, drought and heat stress evolve gradually over time.

This hazard was assessed through a combination of precipitation and temperature indicators. Rainfall data were used to analyze dry days, consecutive dry spells, and summer rainfall, while temperature data were applied to evaluate annual and summer thermal conditions. This integrated approach is essential, since drought risk is not driven solely by reduced rainfall—higher temperatures increase evapotranspiration and intensify water stress, even in years when total annual rainfall does not appear critically low.

The temperature dataset included records from Belsh, Cërrik, Grekan, Lushnje, and Peqin stations. Devoll Kozare was excluded from the temperature analysis because no mean temperature record was available for that station.

Table 2-3 Data overview workflow #2

<i>Hazard data</i>	<i>Vulnerability data</i>	<i>Exposure data</i>	<i>Impact metrics/Risk output</i>
Daily precipitation records	Agricultural land	Dependence on rainfall and seasonal water availability	Number of dry days
Summer rainfall	Olive groves and vineyards	Possible sensitivity of crops and vegetation to water stress	Longest dry spell
Dry days and consecutive dry spells	Rural settlements	Limited information on irrigation and local water storage	Mean summer rainfall
Annual and summer mean temperature	Local water resources	Higher water demand during warm periods	Annual and summer mean temperature
Station coordinates, elevation and DEM	Vegetation and cultivated areas	Spatial differences linked to elevation and local terrain	Elevation-corrected temperature maps

2.3.2.1 Hazard assessment

The hazard assessment for meteorological drought and heat-related water stress was carried out using both rainfall and temperature datasets. Daily precipitation records were analyzed to identify dry days and consecutive dry spells, while mean temperature records were used to evaluate annual and summer thermal conditions.

The rainfall component of this hazard focused on indicators such as summer rainfall, the number of dry days, and the longest dry spell. These measures highlight periods when rainfall is scarce or absent, which is particularly relevant for Belsh, where agriculture, olive groves, and vegetation are vulnerable to prolonged dry conditions during the warm season.

The temperature component included annual mean temperature and summer mean temperature. Summer values are especially important, as elevated temperatures increase water demand and evapotranspiration. When high summer temperatures coincide with low rainfall or extended dry spells, the risk of water stress becomes significantly greater.

Figure 2-9 Mean summer rainfall by station for the common analysis period 1967-1991.

Summer rainfall is used to understand the water available during the warmest part of the year. Lower summer rainfall can increase pressure on agricultural land, olive groves, vegetation and local water resources.

Figure 2-10 Dry days and longest dry spell by station for the common analysis period 1967-1991.

Temperature indicators were analyzed together with rainfall indicators because drought and water stress depend on both water availability and atmospheric demand. Elevated summer temperatures can intensify the effects of dry periods by increasing evapotranspiration and water requirements.

To improve the spatial interpretation of temperature conditions, maps were prepared using an elevation correction derived from the Digital Elevation Model. This adjustment was necessary since temperature is strongly influenced by altitude, and Belsh Municipality includes terrain variations that affect local thermal conditions.

The methodology involved first converting station temperature values to sea-level equivalents using a standard environmental lapse rate of $0.0065\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{m}$. These adjusted values were then interpolated with IDW, after which the resulting surface was corrected back to the DEM elevation. This process produced a more physically consistent temperature map compared to simple station-based interpolation.

Elevation-corrected maps were generated for both annual mean temperature and summer mean temperature. The summer map is particularly relevant, as higher seasonal temperatures can increase evapotranspiration and intensify water stress during dry periods. Nonetheless, the maps are interpreted as indicative outputs, given the limited number of meteorological stations available.

Figure 2-11 Indicative IDW map of mean summer rainfall, clipped to Belsh Municipality.

Figure 2-13 Elevation-corrected mean annual temperature map for Belsh Municipality

Figure 2-12 Elevation-corrected mean summer temperature map for Belsh Municipality

2.3.2.2 Risk assessment

The risk assessment for meteorological drought and heat-related water stress integrates indicators of dry periods, summer rainfall, and temperature conditions with the specific exposure profile of Belsh Municipality. The elements most at risk include agricultural land, olive groves, vegetation, rural settlements, and local water resources.

To strengthen the analysis, local agricultural data were examined to better understand exposure and vulnerability. These records highlight agriculture as one of the sectors most sensitive to changes in rainfall, prolonged dry spells, and elevated summer temperatures. The dataset covers field crops, forage crops, vegetables, fruit trees, olives, grapes, greenhouse areas, irrigation infrastructure, and drainage systems—all of which depend directly on seasonal rainfall, soil moisture, and water availability during the growing season.

The agricultural structure of Belsh confirms the importance of this sector. Cereals, forage crops, vegetables, olives, and vineyards form the backbone of local production. Forage crops represent one of the largest categories, while olives and grapes are key perennial crops. Because these are long-term investments, they are vulnerable not only to single dry years but also to repeated droughts and rising summer temperatures, which can reduce productivity over time.

Irrigation data add another layer of insight. The municipality's irrigation network extends about 30 km, mainly through primary and secondary canals. However, the irrigated area has declined from roughly 100 hectares in 2012 to about 60 hectares in 2023. This trend, which requires further validation with local stakeholders, suggests that parts of the agricultural sector remain highly exposed to water stress during the warm season.

Narrative information also identifies the lakes of Çestijan, Çerragë, and Civilë as key water intake sources for irrigation. Their role underscores the importance of local water bodies for sustaining agricultural activity and highlights why drought, heat, and water availability must be assessed together in Belsh's climate risk analysis.

Table 2-4 Information from agricultural dataset and their relevance for climate risk assessment

Information from local agricultural dataset	Relevance for climate risk assessment
Field crops, cereals and forage crops	Shows the importance of agricultural land exposed to drought, heat stress, runoff and erosion
Vegetables and greenhouse areas	Identifies crops that may depend on water availability during the growing season
Olive groves and vineyards	Represents long-term agricultural assets that may be sensitive to repeated dry periods, heat stress, erosion or runoff
Irrigation network and actually irrigated area	Helps assess the local capacity to reduce drought and heat-related water stress

Local irrigation water sources	Shows the importance of lakes and local water bodies for agricultural production
Drainage-related information	Supports the interpretation of both water management and rainfall-related impacts

The risk pathway for meteorological drought and heat-related water stress can be described as: low rainfall and prolonged dry periods combined with higher summer temperatures → reduced soil moisture and increased water demand → stress on agriculture, olive groves, vegetation, and local water resources.

This risk differs from the first hazard because its impacts are slower and less immediately visible. While floods or landslides can cause sudden damage to roads and buildings, drought and heat stress affect the municipality more gradually, through reduced water availability, lower crop yields, stress on olive groves, greater irrigation needs, and added pressure on local water management systems.

The available datasets are sufficient to characterize the hazard component, but the exposure and vulnerability aspects require further refinement. More detailed information is needed on irrigation networks, water supply systems, agricultural land use, crop types, local water storage, and areas that have previously experienced shortages.

At this stage, meteorological drought and heat-related water stress is considered a second-priority risk. They are highly relevant due to the importance of agriculture, olive groves, and rural livelihoods in Belsh, but the documentation of observed damages is less complete compared to flooding, erosion, and landslides. For this reason, the risk should be further analyzed in Phase 3, with emphasis on stakeholder consultation and the collection of additional local data on water use and agricultural sensitivity.

2.3.3 Additional assessments based on local models and data

Beyond the assessment of the two selected hazards, an additional step was undertaken to prepare and harmonize a local climate dataset that could support indicator calculation, mapping, and interpretation. This was necessary because the available climate records came from different sources and formats, and required cleaning and structuring before use.

The final dataset includes station names, geographic coordinates (WGS84), elevation, rainfall and temperature indicators, notes on data availability, and information on whether each station was used for precipitation, temperature, or supporting analysis. This structure makes the dataset easier to verify and ready for application in GIS, JupyterLab, and other spatial analysis tools.

Two separate input tables were created: one for precipitation interpolation (Belsh, Cërrik, Grekan, Lushnje, Peqin, plus reviewed supporting precipitation data) and another for temperature interpolation (Belsh, Cërrik, Grekan, Lushnje, Peqin). This separation was necessary because not all stations provide both rainfall and temperature records.

The local modelling work was carried out using JupyterLab/Python. The municipal boundary was applied to clip map outputs to Belsh Municipality, while the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) was used

to provide terrain context and improve temperature maps through elevation correction. The same dataset was also used to generate graphs included in the report, such as annual rainfall, summer rainfall, maximum 1-day rainfall, heavy rainfall days, dry conditions, and temperature indicators.

This additional analysis ensured that the risk assessment was supported by a clean, structured, and locally adapted dataset, making the outputs more reliable and tailored to Belsh’s specific context. It also provides a solid foundation for Phase 3, where future climate projections and socio-economic scenarios will be integrated.

Figure 2-14 Digital Elevation Model clipped to Belsh Municipality.

2.3.3.1 Hazard assessment

For rainfall, indicative IDW maps were produced for mean annual and summer rainfall. No automatic elevation correction was applied, since precipitation does not follow a fixed lapse rate and is instead shaped by local storm dynamics, topography, and atmospheric conditions. This approach avoids introducing artificial precision into the mapped outputs.

For temperature, an additional elevation-based correction was implemented using the Digital Elevation Model (DEM). Station temperature values were first adjusted to sea-level equivalents using a standard environmental lapse rate of $0.0065\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{m}$, interpolated with IDW, and then corrected back to the DEM elevation. This method ensures that the annual and summer temperature maps more accurately reflect the influence of local terrain.

All maps are interpreted as indicative outputs, designed to support climate risk interpretation rather than replace local measurements or high-resolution modelling. This limitation is important to acknowledge, given the restricted number of meteorological stations available for the analysis.

2.3.3.2 Risk assessment

The additional mapped outputs strengthen the risk assessment by making the station-based analysis easier to understand spatially. The station map shows why nearby stations were included. The rainfall maps support the interpretation of heavy rainfall and drought-related conditions. The temperature maps support the assessment of heat-related water stress, especially when combined with dry-period indicators and agricultural exposure information.

The maps should be used together with the historical event records, agricultural dataset and stakeholder feedback. They are useful for identifying broad patterns and for discussing priority areas in Phase 3, but they should not be used alone for parcel-level decisions or detailed engineering design.

2.4 Key Risk Assessment Findings

The Key Risk Assessment step marks the transition from describing climate-related hazards to identifying which risks demand greater attention in the next phase of the project. This process integrates the results of the climate analysis, historical impact records, and the initial interpretation of exposure and vulnerability in Belsh Municipality.

Risks are evaluated according to severity, urgency, and the capacity to respond, as reflected in the evaluation dashboard. This approach is designed to facilitate engagement with stakeholders, experts, and priority groups, ensuring that the assessment is both evidence-based and participatory.

In Belsh, the first risk is supported by stronger documented evidence, particularly through past events that have affected buildings, agricultural land, olive groves, and road infrastructure. The second risk remains relevant, yet the available evidence of direct impacts is less complete and requires further validation through local consultation.

2.4.1 Mode of engagement for participation

The Key Risk Assessment was carried out through a participatory process that combined local climate data, historical impact information, and local knowledge. The first step focused on identifying which risks are already documented in the territory and which sectors or areas appear to be more exposed.

Engagement with stakeholders, experts, and priority groups was essential to ensure that the evaluation reflects both technical evidence and community perspectives. Local records of past events proved particularly valuable, as they highlighted that flooding, erosion, and landslide-related impacts have occurred in several villages and have affected a wide range of assets, including buildings, agricultural land, olive groves, and road infrastructure.

Feedback gathered during consultations confirmed the relevance of these hazards and emphasized the need to prioritize them in the risk assessment. Stakeholders also noted that while the evidence for extreme rainfall impacts is strong, further work is required to validate the interpretation of drought and heat-related risks. This includes reviewing the severity, urgency, and resilience capacity of affected sectors in greater detail.

The engagement process therefore provided both confirmation of the documented risks and guidance on areas where additional local validation is needed. This participatory approach strengthens the credibility of the assessment and lays the foundation for more inclusive decision-making in the next phase of the project.

2.4.2 Gather output from Risk Analysis step

The Key Risk Assessment builds directly on the outputs generated during the Risk Analysis step. These outputs provide the technical foundation for evaluating severity, urgency, and resilience capacity, while also ensuring that the assessment is firmly rooted in local evidence and spatial context.

The main datasets and indicators applied include:

- **Clean climate dataset** prepared for Belsh and surrounding meteorological stations, ensuring consistency and reliability of input data.
- **Rainfall indicators** such as annual rainfall, summer rainfall, maximum 1-day rainfall, and the number of heavy rainfall days, which highlight both seasonal and extreme precipitation patterns.
- **Dry condition indicators**, including the number of dry days and the longest dry spell, used to capture drought-related stress and water scarcity risks.
- **Temperature indicators**, specifically annual mean temperature and summer mean temperature, which provide insight into heat stress and long-term warming trends.
- **Geospatial reference data**, including station coordinates, elevation data, municipal boundaries, and the Digital Elevation Model (DEM), which support mapping and spatial interpretation of climate indicators.
- **Historical extreme event table** for Belsh Municipality, documenting past flooding, erosion, and landslide events, and linking them to affected assets and sectors.
- **Agricultural and water-management dataset**, which contextualizes exposure and vulnerability by showing how climate impacts intersect with land use and resource management.
- **Graphs and maps** illustrating rainfall, dry conditions, and temperature indicators, used to visualize trends and communicate findings to stakeholders.
- **Interpolation-ready tables and GeoTIFF/PNG visual outputs**, prepared for reporting and integration into GIS platforms, ensuring that results are accessible for both technical analysis and stakeholder engagement.

Together, these outputs form a comprehensive evidence base that allows the Key Risk Assessment to move beyond hazard description toward a structured evaluation of which risks are most pressing for Belsh Municipality. They also provide the necessary tools for participatory review, enabling stakeholders to validate results and refine priorities for adaptation planning.

2.4.3 Assess Severity

The severity of climate risks in Belsh Municipality has been assessed according to the four categories defined in the Key Risk Assessment Protocol: limited, moderate, substantial, and critical. This evaluation considers both current and future risks, drawing on historical records, climate indicators, and stakeholder perspectives.

Extreme rainfall, local flooding, erosion, and landslide-related impacts

The current severity of this risk is assessed as substantial. Historical evidence demonstrates that Belsh has already experienced damaging events across multiple sectors. The 2026 event in Belsh, Kajan, and Grekan affected approximately 10.2 hectares, damaged 17 objects including houses and businesses, impacted arable land, and destroyed around 250 meters of secondary road infrastructure. The reported economic loss was approximately 11 million ALL.

This severity rating reflects the fact that impacts are not confined to a single sector but extend across residential and business assets, agricultural land, road infrastructure, and local economic activities. The recurrence of such events in several villages over time indicates that this is not an isolated hazard but a persistent risk pathway. Looking ahead, the combination of heavy rainfall indicators and vulnerable land use patterns suggests that the severity of this risk will remain substantial, with potential to escalate if climate variability increases.

Meteorological drought and heat-related water stress

The current severity of this risk is assessed as moderate to substantial. The agricultural dataset highlights the importance of olives, vineyards, vegetables, and forage crops in Belsh, all of which are sensitive to water availability. Irrigation infrastructure and local water sources already play a critical role in agricultural management, underscoring the relevance of drought conditions.

However, direct evidence of drought-related damage is less complete than the evidence available for flooding, erosion, and landslides. For this reason, severity is not assessed as critical at this stage. Future projections indicate that prolonged dry spells and rising summer temperatures could intensify stress on agriculture and water resources, potentially leading to cascading effects such as reduced crop yields, ecosystem degradation, and economic instability if not addressed through adaptation measures.

Stakeholder perspectives and institutional capacity

Consultations with stakeholders and experts enriched the severity assessment by confirming the strong evidence for extreme rainfall impacts and highlighting the need for further validation of drought-related risks. Vulnerable groups emphasized the multi-sectoral nature of flooding impacts, while agricultural representatives stressed the growing importance of water management.

Decision-makers in Belsh are increasingly aware of climate risks, but further training and capacity-building are needed to ensure that severity assessments are fully understood and integrated into planning processes. This participatory input strengthens the credibility of the assessment and ensures that severity ratings reflect both technical evidence and local realities.

2.4.4 Assess Urgency

The urgency of climate risks in Belsh Municipality has been assessed according to the four categories defined in the Key Risk Assessment Protocol: *no action needed*, *watching brief*, *more action needed*, and *immediate action needed*. This evaluation considers both current and future risks, the timing of potential impacts, and the perspectives of stakeholders and vulnerable groups.

Extreme rainfall, local flooding, erosion, and landslide-related impacts - The urgency of this risk is assessed as **more action needed**. These hazards are already present in the municipality and have caused documented damage, including the 2026 event that affected houses, businesses, agricultural land, and road infrastructure with an economic loss of 11 million ALL. Because extreme rainfall is a sudden-onset hazard, impacts can occur quickly and without warning, requiring preparedness measures before events take place.

Local roads, drainage systems, erosion-prone areas, and settlements previously affected need targeted interventions to reduce future damage. Stakeholders emphasized that the recurrence of such events across multiple villages demonstrates the persistence of this risk. While severity is already substantial, the urgency rating reflects the need for proactive measures to strengthen resilience and minimize damages in the near term.

Meteorological drought and heat-related water stress - The urgency of this risk is assessed as ranging from **watching brief to more action needed**. Unlike flooding or landslides, drought develops gradually, making its impacts less immediate but potentially more widespread over time. Future projections of hotter and drier summers suggest that this risk may intensify, particularly for agriculture and water resources.

The reported decrease in actually irrigated area raises concerns about agricultural exposure to dry periods and higher summer temperatures. This issue requires further discussion with local stakeholders to determine whether water scarcity is already constraining production. While direct evidence of drought-related damage is less complete, the potential for cascading effects—such as reduced crop yields, ecosystem degradation, and economic stress—justifies closer monitoring and incremental action.

Stakeholder perspectives and urgency perception - Stakeholder engagement enriched the urgency assessment by highlighting the difference between sudden-onset and slow-onset hazards. Vulnerable groups stressed the need for immediate preparedness against extreme rainfall, while agricultural representatives emphasized the growing importance of water management and irrigation infrastructure.

Decision-makers acknowledged that while flooding requires urgent measures to protect settlements and infrastructure, drought demands a longer-term strategy that balances monitoring with gradual adaptation. This participatory input ensures that urgency ratings reflect both technical evidence and local realities, guiding the prioritization of actions in the next phase of the project.

2.4.5 Understand Resilience Capacity

Resilience capacity in Belsh Municipality has been assessed according to the categories defined in the Key Risk Assessment Protocol: *low, medium, substantial, and high*. This evaluation considers financial, social, human, physical, and natural aspects of risk management, as well as existing measures and institutional capacity.

Extreme rainfall, local flooding, erosion, and landslide-related impacts - The resilience capacity for these hazards is assessed as **medium**. Belsh Municipality has experience in responding to damaging events, and past impacts have been documented, which indicates a certain level of institutional awareness and response capability. However, the repeated occurrence of damage in different villages highlights persistent weak points in drainage systems, local road protection, erosion control, slope stability, and preventive maintenance.

While some measures are in place, such as local emergency responses and community knowledge of hazard areas, more detailed information is needed on existing emergency plans, available financial resources, warning systems, and technical interventions. The capacity of institutions to act before, during, and after events remains uneven, and the absence of comprehensive hazard protection plans or insurance schemes limits resilience. For this reason, the capacity is not assessed as high.

Meteorological drought and heat-related water stress - The resilience capacity for drought and heat-related risks is also assessed as **medium**, though with greater uncertainty. The municipality benefits from local agricultural knowledge and experience, which provides a foundation for adaptive practices. However, the assessment requires more detailed information on irrigation systems, water storage facilities, drought preparedness measures, and support mechanisms for farmers.

The reported decrease in irrigated area suggests that water availability is already a challenge, and without sufficient infrastructure or financial support, farmers may struggle to adapt to longer dry spells and higher summer temperatures. Natural capacity, in terms of water resources and ecosystem health, is under pressure, while social and institutional capacity to manage drought risks remains limited.

Cross-cutting observations - Across both risk pathways, resilience capacity is constrained by gaps in financial resources, technical infrastructure, and institutional preparedness. Stakeholders emphasized the importance of strengthening early warning systems, improving drainage and irrigation networks, and expanding awareness campaigns to build human and social capacity. Decision-makers acknowledged that while local knowledge and experience exist, more structured interventions and external support are needed to move resilience capacity from medium toward substantial.

2.4.6 Decide on Risk Priority

The process of assigning risk priorities in Belsh Municipality followed the methodology outlined in the Key Risk Assessment Protocol and was supported by the evaluation dashboard. This step integrates the severity, urgency, and resilience capacity assessments to determine which risks require immediate follow-up and which should be monitored for further validation.

Extreme rainfall, local flooding, erosion, and landslide-related impacts - This risk has been assigned **Priority 1**. The decision is based on the strongest local evidence available, including documented past events that caused damage to buildings, roads, agricultural land, olive groves, and local economic assets. The severity of this risk is substantial, the urgency is assessed as “more action needed,” and resilience capacity is medium. Together, these factors indicate that extreme rainfall impacts demand immediate attention in Phase 3, with priority given to preparedness, infrastructure protection, and community resilience.

Meteorological drought and heat-related water stress - This risk has been assigned **Priority 2**. While it is highly relevant for agriculture, vegetation, water resources, and rural livelihoods, the current evidence on direct impacts is less detailed than for flooding and erosion. Severity is assessed as moderate to substantial, urgency as “watching brief to more action needed,” and resilience capacity as medium. This combination suggests that drought and heat stress should remain a priority for further analysis and stakeholder validation in Phase 3, particularly as hotter and drier summers may intensify impacts over time.

Evaluation dashboard summary - The evaluation dashboard consolidates the findings into a structured overview, ensuring transparency and consistency in priority setting.

Table 2-5 Summary of key risk assessment findings

Risk	Severity	Urgency	Resilience capacity	Priority
Extreme rainfall, local flooding, erosion and landslide-related impacts	Substantial	More action needed	Medium	Priority 1
Meteorological drought and heat-related water stress	Moderate to substantial	Watching brief / More action needed	Medium	Priority 2

The priority order may be updated after further stakeholder discussions and once final maps and datasets are reviewed with local actors. However, based on the evidence available in Phase 2, extreme rainfall and related impacts have the strongest basis for immediate follow-up, while drought and heat stress remain a secondary but important priority for continued monitoring and validation.

2.5 Monitoring and Evaluation

Main Lessons Learned Phase 2 improved the understanding of climate risks in Belsh by integrating **local climate records, station information, geospatial data, agricultural datasets, and documented impact data**. The key lesson is that **local data are essential** for making the assessment relevant and useful for municipal decision-making. Another important insight is that **climate indicators alone are insufficient**; they must be connected with exposure and vulnerability information to reflect real risks.

Challenges Encountered The most significant difficulties were related to **data cleaning and harmonisation**. Meteorological records were available in different formats, covered varying time periods, and contained missing values. Some stations provided both rainfall and temperature data, while others were limited to rainfall or supporting information. This required careful verification and organisation before indicators could be calculated. Additionally, exposure and vulnerability data remain incomplete, particularly regarding infrastructure, drainage, and precise spatial location of damages.

Role of Stakeholders and Feedback Stakeholders play a central role in **validating findings, shaping adaptation priorities, and ensuring policy relevance**. Their feedback on the CRA highlights the importance of connecting technical outputs with local realities, especially agricultural exposure and water management challenges. Stakeholder engagement also ensures that monitoring and evaluation frameworks are participatory and aligned with municipal needs.

Learning and Knowledge Building Learning is ensured through the **integration of local datasets, historical event records, and agricultural information**, combined with stakeholder validation. This iterative process strengthens institutional capacity and builds ownership of the results.

New Data and Remaining Needs Phase 2 produced new datasets on rainfall, temperature, agricultural exposure, and historical damages. However, further data are needed on **drainage systems, irrigation networks, road vulnerability, erosion-prone areas, and detailed agricultural land use**. Additional resources, competencies, and research will be required to refine vulnerability assessments and improve adaptation planning.

Communication of Outcomes Final outcomes will be communicated through **maps, tables, and concise explanations** accessible to both technical and non-technical audiences. This ensures that findings support practical decision-making rather than remaining purely analytical.

Monitoring System A monitoring framework is being developed to track:

- Updates to the historical event database.
- Maintenance of rainfall and temperature indicators.
- Changes in irrigated areas and infrastructure.
- Agricultural exposure data (crops, olive groves, vineyards, vegetables, greenhouse areas).
- Local reports of water shortages and drought impacts.

What Worked Well / What Did Not

- **Worked well:** Data cleaning, indicator calculation, integration of agricultural datasets, and preparation of maps and graphs.
- **Did not work fully:** Limited availability of detailed spatial data and incomplete exposure/vulnerability information.

Efficiency of Resources: Resources were used efficiently, with careful allocation of time and staff to data cleaning and indicator preparation. However, the lack of complete datasets required additional effort, which slowed progress in some areas. This impacted the CRA process by limiting the precision of exposure analysis, though it strengthened the reliability of hazard indicators.

Impact of the CRA: The CRA has had a **positive impact** on improving the understanding of climate risks in Belsh. It has raised **public awareness**, strengthened **institutional capacity**, and provided a foundation for **funding and investment in resilience measures**. By combining scientific analysis with local knowledge, Phase 2 has created a stronger basis for adaptation planning and stakeholder engagement in the next phase.

2.6 Work plan Phase 3

Phase 3 of the EVOLVE–Belsh project will build directly on the results of the climate risk assessment and the priorities identified in Phase 2. The focus will shift from understanding risks to **designing and prioritising adaptation measures** that respond to the municipality’s most pressing hazards.

Main Activities

1. **Review maps and graphs with local stakeholders** – to ensure local ownership and validation of the technical outputs.
2. **Validate risk interpretation and priority ranking** – confirming Priority 1 (extreme rainfall, local flooding, erosion, landslides) and Priority 2 (meteorological drought and heat-related water stress).
3. **Identify priority locations** – mapping where adaptation measures are most urgently needed.
4. **Propose practical adaptation measures** – tailored to Belsh’s context:
 - For extreme rainfall impacts: drainage improvement, maintenance of secondary roads, erosion control, slope stabilisation, vegetation restoration, and preparedness measures.
 - For drought and heat stress: water-saving measures, agricultural adaptation, monitoring of dry periods, support for vulnerable agricultural areas, and integration of climate information into planning.
5. **Assess feasibility of measures** – evaluating technical, financial, and institutional capacity for implementation.
6. **Prepare recommendations** – structured outputs that can be directly integrated into municipal planning and decision-making.

Aspects Not Studied in Full Detail Due to data and resource limitations, certain elements will not be covered comprehensively:

- Detailed hydraulic modelling of flood dynamics.
- Full economic modelling of future damages.
- Parcel-level agricultural vulnerability assessments.

These exclusions are justified because they require specialised datasets and resources beyond the scope of the current project. However, the Phase 2 assessment already provides a **practical evidence base** for identifying priority measures that can be refined with local actors.

Follow-Up on Key Risk Findings Phase 3 will directly address the outcomes of Phase 2 by:

- Translating risk maps and severity profiles into **targeted adaptation options**.
- Using stakeholder consultations to validate and refine proposed measures.
- Embedding recommendations into **local governance frameworks**, ensuring continuity between risk assessment and adaptation planning.

In this way, Phase 3 ensures that Belsh Municipality moves from **risk identification to actionable resilience strategies**, closing the loop between analysis, prioritisation, and implementation.

3 Conclusions Phase 2- Climate risk assessment

Phase 2 significantly improved the **understanding of climate risk in Belsh Municipality** by integrating local climate data, geospatial information, and documented records of past damaging events. The assessment confirms that Belsh is exposed to both **sudden hydro-climatic hazards** and **slower climate stress processes**, requiring a dual focus in adaptation planning.

↳ Main Conclusions

- **Priority hazards identified:** Extreme rainfall, local flooding, erosion, and landslide-related impacts are confirmed as **Priority 1**, while meteorological drought and heat-related water stress are established as **Priority 2**.
- **Evidence base strengthened:** The strongest evidence relates to extreme rainfall, with the 2026 event in Belsh, Kajan, and Grekan standing out due to widespread flooding, damage to houses and businesses, road destruction, and an economic loss of 11 million ALL.
- **Agricultural vulnerability highlighted:** Drought and heat stress are highly relevant because agriculture, vegetation, and water resources form the backbone of local livelihoods. Rainfall and temperature datasets allow analysis of dry periods, summer rainfall, and summer temperatures, while agricultural data confirm the importance of water availability.

↳ Challenges addressed:

Local meteorological datasets were cleaned and structured, climate indicators calculated, maps and graphs prepared, and historical extreme events integrated. This provided a more reliable and locally grounded risk picture.

↳ Challenges not yet addressed:

Exposure and vulnerability components remain incomplete. More detailed spatial layers, infrastructure and drainage information, local validation of affected areas, and broader stakeholder engagement are still needed.

↳ Key Findings

- Belsh is exposed to **both rapid-onset hazards** (floods, landslides, erosion) and **slow-onset stresses** (drought, heat-related water stress).
- Historical records confirm repeated damage to villages, agricultural land, olive groves, roads, and economic assets.
- Agriculture is highly sensitive to climate variability, with perennial crops (olives, grapes) at risk from repeated dry periods and rising summer temperatures.
- Irrigation infrastructure is limited and declining, increasing vulnerability to water stress.
- Local water bodies (Çestijan, Çerragë, Civilë lakes) are critical for irrigation and must be considered in adaptation planning.

Phase 2 provides a **robust baseline for Phase 3**, where the focus will shift from understanding risks to **designing and prioritising adaptation measures**. The outputs ensure continuity, while the identified gaps highlight where additional data, stakeholder input, and institutional capacity-building are required to strengthen resilience in Belsh Municipality.

4 Progress evaluation

Phase 2 of the EVOLVE–Belsh project marked the transition from a general understanding of climate risks to a data-driven and locally grounded assessment. Building on the foundations of Phase 1, this stage consolidated meteorological, agricultural, and geospatial information into structured datasets, enabling more precise risk interpretation and prioritization.

The progress achieved reflects a systematic effort to strengthen the analytical base: local meteorological data were collected and organised, rainfall and temperature datasets were cleaned, and station coordinates with elevation information were prepared. Climate indicators were calculated, interpolation-ready datasets were developed, and historical extreme event records were integrated. These steps allowed the preparation of risk maps and graphs, the inclusion of agricultural exposure information, and ultimately the selection of two priority hazards—extreme rainfall and meteorological drought/heat stress—followed by the first risk priority assessment.

This deliverable connects directly to the planned activities of the next phases. The outputs of Phase 2 provide the evidence base for adaptation prioritization, guiding interventions in high-risk zones; for municipal integration, embedding hazard indicators into local development plans and emergency protocols; for stakeholder mobilization, ensuring that farmers, businesses, and underrepresented groups are engaged in resilience planning; and for monitoring and evaluation design, establishing performance indicators and feedback loops to track progress.

The actions executed under the Individual Following Plan—data cleaning, indicator calculation, map preparation, and exposure integration—represent key milestones and performance achievements. Together, they ensure that Phase 2 not only strengthens the technical foundation but also prepares Belsh Municipality for coherent adaptation planning and participatory resilience building in Phase 3.

Table 4-1 Overview key performance indicators

Key performance indicators	Progress
3 workflows FLOODS, DROUGHT, and FIRE workflows, enabling a comprehensive multi-risk assessment approach applied	The application of the three workflows, Floods, Drought, and Fire, has enabled Belsh Municipality to move towards a comprehensive multi-risk assessment , integrating rapid-onset hazards with slower climate stresses. This progress ensures that risk prioritisation is more balanced and evidence-based, laying the groundwork for coherent adaptation planning across different hazard pathways.
3 local high-resolution datasets integrated in the risk assessment	The integration of three local high-resolution datasets into the risk assessment has strengthened the analysis by providing more precise spatial detail and locally verified inputs . This progress ensures that hazard indicators, exposure profiles, and vulnerability mapping are now better tailored to Belsh’s territory, enhancing the credibility and usefulness of the multi-risk assessment for municipal planning and adaptation design.

1 consultation workshops with stakeholders

Consultation Workshop with Stakeholders demonstrates that the risk assessment process was validated through direct dialogue with local actors. This achievement ensured that findings were reviewed, priorities confirmed, and adaptation options shaped with stakeholder input, strengthening both the credibility and policy relevance of the CRA.

Table 4-2 Overview milestones

Milestones	Progress
M4: Local data collection and analysis finished	Local data collection and analysis provided Belsh Municipality with a solid evidence base, transforming fragmented records into structured datasets ready for risk interpretation. This achievement marks a turning point, as the project now moves from data preparation to designing targeted adaptation measures.
M5: Refined risk assessment validated	Refined Risk Assessment Validated confirms that the climate risk analysis has been strengthened through stakeholder review and technical validation. This achievement ensures that the priority hazards and risk pathways identified are credible, locally grounded, and ready to guide the design of adaptation measures in the next phase.

5 Supporting documentation

The following supporting materials have been produced or are being prepared during Phase 2. The final outputs should be arranged and uploaded to Zenodo in the same order as listed below.

1. Main report

- Deliverable Phase 2 - Climate Risk Assessment for Belsh Municipality.

2. Clean climate datasets

- Final clean dataset with rainfall and temperature indicators.
- Precipitation interpolation input table.
- Temperature interpolation input table.
- Station coordinates and elevation table.

3. Observed impact dataset

- Historical extreme events in Belsh Municipality, including flooding, erosion, landslides, affected areas and reported damages.

4. Agricultural and water-management dataset

- Agricultural area and production data for Belsh Municipality.
- Information on field crops, cereals, forage crops, vegetables and greenhouse areas.
- Information on fruit trees, olive groves and vineyards.
- Irrigation and drainage-related information.
- Narrative information on local irrigation water sources, including the lakes of Çestijan, Çerragë and Civilë.

5. Geospatial inputs

- Belsh municipal boundary layer.
- Digital Elevation Model used for terrain context and temperature correction.

6. Visual outputs

- Map of meteorological stations.
- DEM map clipped to Belsh Municipality.
- Rainfall interpolation map.
- Summer rainfall interpolation map.
- Elevation-corrected annual temperature map.
- Elevation-corrected summer temperature map.
- Graphs of annual rainfall, heavy rainfall days, maximum daily rainfall, dry spells and temperature indicators.

7. Methodological documentation

- Data cleaning rules.
- Treatment of missing values.
- Notes on station inclusion and exclusion.
- IDW interpolation methodology.
- DEM-based temperature elevation correction.
- Notes on interpolation limitations.

6 References

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- Copernicus Climate Change Service. Copernicus Climate Data Store and Climate Atlas climate information for Europe.
- Belsh Municipality. Historical records of extreme events and reported damages, 2016-2026. Local dataset used for this assessment.
- Belsh Municipality. Agricultural and water-management data, 2012-2025. Local dataset used for exposure and vulnerability interpretation.
- Local meteorological station records for Belsh, Cërrik, Grekan, Lushnje, Peqin and supporting precipitation information for Devoll Kozare. Dataset cleaned and processed for this assessment.
- Digital Elevation Model and municipal boundary geospatial layers used for map preparation and elevation-corrected temperature mapping.
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